

PARENTS AS STUDY BUDDIES: THE ROLE OF THE PARENTS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MODULAR LEARNING PROGRAM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

2023

Volume: 8

Pages: 426-450

Document ID: 2023PEMJ663

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7868663

Manuscript Accepted: 2023-25-4

Parents as Study Buddies: The Role of the Parents in the Implementation of Modular Learning Program

Joel C. Gutierrez*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This descriptive phenomenological study explored the role of parents as study buddies of their children in implementing the modular learning program. An in-depth interview was used to gather the lived experiences of 16 parents purposely chosen to participate in the study. The parents included are either male or female, with at least two children studying in public schools and have not gone to school or completed elementary level. Their personal narratives about their experiences, their coping mechanisms to address the struggles encountered, their learnings, and insights from their experiences as a study guide of their children in the modular learning were gathered using a semi-structured interview guide. The data collected were analyzed using Colaizzi's method for data analysis. Findings reveal that parents' learning experiences are varied; they are glad to engage in their children's learning and can learn while assisting them with their module activities. Parents face challenges in comprehension modules, time management, and parental literacy, but they overcome them by seeking assistance from relatives, using the internet, and praying for wisdom. Despite their challenges, they understand the value of education for their children's future and realize that education is the only weapon that can be used to face life's challenges.

Keywords: *parents, study buddies, lived experiences, phenomenology*

Introduction

Education is the most precious thing that parents can provide to their children. Through education, the doors for a better future were opened for their children to cope with the standard of the new generation. In the education process, the parents become the study buddies of their children and coordinate with the teachers for the educational development in terms of effective teaching and learning process. The worldwide issues pertain to the health crisis; Jordan has faced the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic and made rapid and firm decisions that have helped limit the spread of the virus. Under these circumstances, education officials have sought to find optimal alternative teaching and learning methods that contribute to the sustainability of the teaching and learning process. The solution was a digital transformation in teaching, learning, and digital applications to accomplish distance learning or web-based learning (Hamaidi et al., 2021).

However, despite the efforts to assist parents in this daunting task of educating their children at home, struggles are inevitable (Garbe et al., 2020). For example, Lee et al. (2020) recounted that amid the acute phase of the health crisis, half of the American parents in their survey felt overwhelmed by the responsibilities to educate their child at home, resulting in significant depression and moderate or severe anxiety. Dong et al. (2020) also uncovered that Chinese parents view and experience implementing

online learning amid the COVID-19 crisis as challenging, especially since some needed to be trained or ready to adopt online learning.

In the Philippine educational context, Manila Times (2020) they have extolled parents' crucial role in implementing various remote learning modalities amid the COVID-19 crisis. Public schools are modular, where one hundred percent of the learning is placed in the hands of students and parents. There have been several feedbacks heard on the delivery mode, whether a parent can successfully assist the learning activity of their children, considering factors like their educational attainment, far-flung residence, an occupation which might entail a 24/7 physical presence, and their traditional knowledge of the core subjects may not jibe with the changes in the curriculum.

Here in the Division of Cotabato, particularly in Midsayap, it is observed that many module tasks need to be completed or answered. According to the conversation with some parents who personally returned the modules of their children, they need help assessing their children when it comes to module contents.

This prompted the researcher to assess the role of parents as direct facilitators and support services during the implementation of the Modular Learning Program.

Research Questions

The qualitative study explored the parents' lived experiences as their children's study buddies during the implementation of the Modular Learning Program.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How would the parents describe their experiences as study buddies of their children?
2. How do parents cope with their children's challenges as study buddies?
3. What learnings from their experiences as study buddies of their children can they share with other parents?
4. What insights can the parents share as study buddies of their children?

Literature Review

The Role of Parents in Education

The Filipino family is highly patriarchal, where the father serves as the breadwinner, and the mother, as the house manager; from household chores to child-rearing and the teaching of the young revolves around her. Everything was first learned in the family, with the mother as the teacher. Parents are considered their child's first teacher when a child is born. As they grow into adults, parents' typical roles include teaching, guiding, and raising children to become vital members of their communities (Ceka & Murati, 2016). LaRoque et al. (as mentioned by Alicamen et al., 2020) expounded that parents' responses and participation in modular teaching are affected by various factors, including their educational attainment, self-esteem, motivation, comfort level, language skills, and socio-demographic profile. Educators should make parental involvement more familiar and meaningful. This will promote the participation of parents. It is vital to note parental involvement as a process rather than a one-time occasion to encourage parents to enhance their capacity to help their children get the best possible education.

Since education is no longer held in schools, parents are essential as learning facilitators and para-teachers that provide learners with instructional support without a classroom teacher. Parents are also the most critical factors in their prior achievements as their children's first teachers. When parents and children work together on educational activities, their attachment expands since they can spend more time around each other. Such instances allow parents to become a source of comfort in easing pain and worry and engage in

conversations with their children to help alleviate their anxiety. It has been recommended that parents should be taught interventions on how to provide emotional support to children at times of uncertainty (Wang et al., 2020). Seale (2020) suggests that one of the best ways to prevent deep divisions and educational inequalities during the epidemic is to empower families to support learning in their homes.

However, this modality, modular distance learning, encounter various challenges, particularly in the Philippines. Tibon (2020) elucidates that many learners in primary education need to be proficient in independent learning, while several learners are not supported by their guardians and parents. In addition, the formulation and production of quality modules to address the varying needs of the learners need some consideration. Lastly, the holistic development of the learners might be affected. Students may have few chances to interact and socialize. This can pose a problem for students who need help coping with the drastic educational transformation. Luaña (2021) mentioned that featured themes were complex for students due to challenging terminology and ideas. To counter this, parents explain issues to their children simply to the best of their ability. Parents explain complicated sentences their children cannot understand and believe that by doing so, their children will grasp the gist of the lessons, which will aid them in answering the questions in their modules. Similarly, when their child encounters difficulty reading and comprehending English texts, Parents translate the lessons into Filipino for their children to understand and answer what is indicated in their module and then guide them by giving examples. Parents help and guide their children by providing additional examples not included in the modules.

According to Mercader and Abadiano (2020), although many parents have struggled to get their children to learn, many have attempted to welcome technology and deal with online learning. Their study indicated that many mothers have been using the Facebook application to connect with the social media community to help their children become more interested in their home learning activities. Moreover, according to Malanga, as mentioned by Gevero, M. (2021), parents provide their children with a conducive learning environment to help them focus more on learning and regularly check their child's schedule or workweek plan. Because of the number of subjects or activities to be done, parents and guardians must see that it is being followed accordingly to avoid cramming or delays in submission, which may affect the child's performance. Parents also obtain the

different materials and services needed by the learner. Moreover, give adequate praise, encouragement, and rewards to heighten their child's learning motivation.

Likewise, Jaiswal (2017) concurred that parents also involved themselves in helping their children, improving their schoolwork, providing encouragement, arranging appropriate study time and space, model desired behavior (such as reading for pleasure), monitoring homework, and actively monitoring their children tutoring their children at home. According to Ezeokoli and Ugwu (2019), parents use their mother tongue to communicate their ideas better and explain concepts to their children. This bears similarity with the study of Luaña (2021), who stated that many subject areas used English as the medium of instruction in writing the modules; thus, parents translate the lessons to Filipino content for their child's better understanding of the module. Moreover, parents guide their children by explaining and giving examples without explicitly giving them the answers, acting as a guide on the side and allowing their children to participate actively in the learning process.

Strategies for Engaging Parents

Parental engagement is critical to student achievement (Kim, 2020). Parental engagement is the active participation of parents in all aspects of their children's social, emotional, and academic development (Castro et al., 2015). The level of involvement changes due to the parents' abilities and expectations, differing student needs, and shared responsibility with teachers (Borup et al., 2015; Keaton & Gilbert, 2020). Parents or guardians are partners of teachers in education. They serve as home facilitators and para-teachers who facilitate and guide the students in answering the modular lessons they sent during modular learning (Manlangit et al., 2020). Depending on the administrators' schedules, parents and guardians pick up the school's self-learning modules (DepEd, 2020). The Philippine Information Agency (2020) shares that parental guidance and support will incentivize children to learn. Studies revealed that parental participation, such as modular distance learning, is the missing link in educational equity in this educational setup. Even the most established schools and teachers must do more than educate every child independently.

According to Lee et al. (2022), to motivate children and to release working parents from stress, parents can do the following six things: (a) manage our stress - taking deep breaths, exercising, meditating, and practicing mindfulness can help us manage our stress;

(b) let go of control on kids - it often becomes a source of stress that hurts their motivation and diminishes their ability to learn; (c) encourage learning, not doing; (d) encourage them to learn and to use homework to strengthen their knowledge. If they still refuse to do homework, let them face the natural consequences; (e) focus on relationships instead of homework - a warm, secure parent-child relationship in childhood is essential to living a happy, successful life; and (f) be supportive and teach stress awareness - when a child is not motivated to learn, be supportive instead of contemptuous.

In a world of dual-income households, single-parent households, and unconventional work hours, they should provide multiple opportunities to fit engagement and interaction into their schedules. Cooper (2021) recommended innovative ways to fuel parental involvement: (a) online advice video - teachers can guide how parents can help with specific assignments, and parents can provide feedback on areas where their child may need extra help; (b) use social media at your school to connect to parents - social media provides excellent ways to connect parents to your school's website and begin engaging them; and (c) home visits and parent/teacher conferences.

Learning at Home

The home learning environment combines activities and spaces that affect a child's development and learning. It provides opportunities for them to interact with books, objects, and everyday experiences to make sense of their world. The most important feature, though, is their interactions with people who provide the love, security, encouragement, conversation, and positive role models to help their child to thrive. A good home learning environment encourages children and young people to have positive attitudes toward learning, curiosity, and self-confidence (Parent Zone, 2020).

Parents' experience and expertise are believed to be priceless. According to studies, one of the best predictors of a child's success in school is learning at home and parents being involved in their children's education. Parental involvement helps develop self-confidence and motivation in the classroom. Parents who help their children have many benefits, including strengths and weaknesses, spending individual time with children, enlightening, making learning more meaningful, and having higher aspirations (Kiser, 2020). According to (Malarbas, 2022), parental involvement at home influences children in a positive

way. One of the practical reasons for parents involved is that it helps relieve stress and anxiety for students struggling with their lessons. Parents with experience and expertise in various subjects and life experiences help increase relevance to children. Also, parents who help their children comprehend the lesson's content and make it more meaningful are of immense help for them to understand.

According to Wang et al. (2020), when parents and their children spend more time together, it is likely a good bond where they can work together more in a child's learning activities. In addition, it states that the more parents are open and have time with their children may allow their children to understand that they are present when they need hope and comfort, easing their pain and worry and even alleviating their pain and worry their anxiety. It has been recommended that programs and interventions be taught to parents to have ideas and an understanding of how they should provide emotional support to their children when needed. As suggested by Zahed, Rezaee, Yazdani, Bagheri, and Nabeiei (2016), it is a highly significant component of parenting associated with the training and growth of talents, skills, the learning about social rules and norms, as well as choices of interests in the forms of hobbies that can transform in careers when both having close relationships and mutual understanding between parents and children. Therefore, high levels of parents' involvement in the learning and disciplining of children could have a reverse effect on accomplishment (Hosokawa & Katsura, 2018).

In Pakistan, more must be done nationally to manage the educational crisis during the pandemic. Overall, Pakistan has 8,636,383 students enrolled in pre-primary institutes, whereas students enrolled in primary and secondary schools are 22,931,305 and 13,357,618, respectively (UNESCO, COVID-19 Educational Disruption and Response, 2020). The private educational system across Pakistan has opted to give children homework so they may adhere to the curriculum planned for the year; however, they later announced summer vacations when the situation provoked unpredictability (Hasan, 2020). Despite restricted access to the Internet, online classes are being held at the university level (Ali, 2020). Schools and colleges have been asked to promote children to the next grade (Saeed, 2020), and low-cost schools are on the brink of closure due to the crisis (Yousafzai, 2020).

Experiences of Parents in Modular Distance Learning

The teachers, learners, and their parents must adapt to homeschooling with the new instructional modality. Distance learning requires parents as learning supervisors, tutors, and homeschooling teachers. This confirms a previous study that parents actively implement child education at home during the COVID-19 pandemic (Hapsari et al., 2020). Therefore, even working for the family, the parents should also have the same readiness to educate children in learning education at home. This is because high levels of involvement of the parents in the learner's homeschooling can obtain positive achievement results, even without assistance from a school or teacher.

Meanwhile, other parents generally had negative attitudes about the benefits of online learning. They preferred traditional learning because of the hardships caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, their children's inadequate self-regulation, and their lack of time and professional knowledge to support online learning (Dong et al., 2020). Parents struggle to balance responsibilities, learner motivation, accessibility, and learning outcomes (Garbe et al., 2020). Regarding the learners' motivation and learning outcomes, the parents observe the lack of attention to lessons; difficulty in coping with fast pacing of instructions; inability to finish the desired outputs; and health-related problems. Students' attitudes, learning styles, and lifestyle adjustments influence the learning outcomes of the students (Lukong et al., 2020).

Puspita (2021) pointed out how crucial parents, particularly mothers, are in educating their children. Parent serves as direct guidance on their children's reading, writing, and with their home tasks. Several factors made parental involvement more difficult during these stressful times (Soriano et al., 2022). Due to lack of vocabulary, mastery of the teachings, and English communication, comprehension abilities, and poverty hampered parents' ability to assist their children intellectually, leading them to use a variety of dispensed parenting techniques such as using Google Translate to translate unfamiliar words, searching the Internet for needed information, consulting a dictionary to resolve vocabulary issues, and enlisting the help of more knowledgeable relatives (Budao, 2021). As Paco et al. (2021) stated, parents found it challenging to carry out their duties and obligations to assist children at home. Parents cannot just play their significant role as parents but as educators. Being passed down the duties and responsibilities mainly belonging to teachers have significantly affected their decisions on what to give more time between household chores and educating their children.

Another study is by Constantino et al. (2020), who stated that parents, amidst online distance learning, disliked how modules could have been better printed. These are issues such as seeing unsuitable colors for models and having pieces that could be easier to read. Luaña (2021) listed how parents help their children answer modules by explaining, providing examples, correcting their children's incorrect answers, 'Googling' the answer, and directly providing the correct answers. On the other hand, Luaña listed three methods for parents to help their children answer modules: explaining, giving examples, and correcting their children's inaccurate answers; guiding by 'Googling' the solution; and leading by immediately delivering the proper answers. Luaña points out that some featured themes were complex for pupils to grasp due to complicated vocabulary and concepts. To combat this, parents do their utmost to explain complex subjects to their children in simple words. Parents feel that explaining difficult words to their children would help them understand the gist of the teachings, which will help them answer the problems in their modules.

Further, Olivo (2021), stated that it is a significant disadvantage when parents have inadequate knowledge of specific topics. That would enable them to assist their children properly. Likewise, the same thing goes when it comes to time for other priorities at home, which is not enough, to answer the myriad of activities. Amora (2022) shows support by demonstrating that most parents face challenges such as being unable to remember preceding knowledge, being drained by the circumstance, financial status, and intermittent connections. Bayod et al. (2021) elaborated on the difficulty of a mother in teaching their children since she does not know the answers to the questions because she has not even reached high school for which the level of the lesson is about and that it is better to have a personal session with the teacher so that clear explanations about the lessons will be given.

According to Garbe et al. (2020), parents struggle to balance their obligations, learner motivation, accessibility, and learning outcomes. In addition, a similar study by Kintanar et al. (2021), seeking to understand the parents' difficulties when facing administrated Modular Distance Learning, stated that some parents need to be more knowledgeable when facilitating their children. Gecolea and Gecolea (2021) revealed that parents best support their children by sharing inputs, perspectives, and provisions for the student's needs. The experiences of unsung heroes of modular learning are the parents' role in delivering the

learning, their exploration of ways and strategies to attain the students' attention, as a support channel and good provider assistant in imposing learning at home. Palma et al. (2021), even though parents have shortcomings, parents know their integral role in their children's learning, which can affect academic performance.

Schools began to train parents for the flow of modular distance learning. Parents were advised on the learning delivery modality they wanted for their children. In addition, they were also told about their vital role in this period of the pandemic, which is to act as a learning facilitator for their children at home. They often take their position as an additional workload and challenge because they need more patience and ability to teach the lessons to their children. They internalize their new position for their children with a series of orientations. Schools also had orientation for students to understand the changes that are taking place in the new education system. They were told that their home would act as their school for the entire period of modular distance learning. Their teachers would be their parents or older siblings with the capacity and ability to clarify the substance of the lessons. Modules, learning activity sheets, and other additional materials are given. These learning packages are distributed and retrieved every Friday. As a result, they are given one week to perform all the learning tasks listed in their learning guides (Canonizado, 2021).

Modesty aside, the modular approach promises learner-centered, flexibility, accessibility, simplicity, and cost-efficiency modalities to save a lot on transportation and accommodation (Ambayon, 2020). On the other side, parents or guardians face various dilemmas in assisting their children; 1) if parents or guardians are full-time workers, 2) Elementary and High School undergraduates, 3) low-income workers, 4) jobless due to the pandemic, and 5) parents or guardians cannot afford to buy loads to access their teachers whenever they have queries. The threat to the safety and well-being of the learners and family members at home becomes everybody's concern. It shall facilitate the learning experience must be done at the convenience of their homes while doing some learning tasks (Ibyatova et al., 2018). The learning activities presented by the different modules through multiple subjects ranging from seven to nine (7-9) impact all the school community members' lives (Department of Education Order No. 18 s. 2020, n.d.) (Department of Education Order No. 12 s. 2020, n.d.). As the Agency moderates prevailing conditions, all concerned are reminded to return or release without fail the Module Key Answers with the corrected

submitted modules to help the parents, guardians, and facilitators monitor the learner's progress (Department of Education Division Memorandum No. 265, n.d.) (Department of Education Order No. 001 s. 2021, n.d.). Given its prevailing challenges, it is now one way of reaching out to stakeholders to moderate the modular approach's impact.

Models of Parental Involvement

Educators and parents play critical roles in students' educational performance. Students need a supportive learning environment that provides encouragement, motivation, and high-quality instruction to excel in school. With growing demands on families, parental involvement in their children's education expands beyond the classroom. While balancing education, sports, family situations, family time, job schedules, and other obligations, many families face daunting and volatile schedules and circumstances, leaving little time to provide help in any place (Durisic et al. (2017).

Dr. Joyce Epstein of Johns Hopkins University has developed a framework for defining six types of parent involvement. This framework assists educators in developing school and family partnership programs. First, parenting: help all families establish home environments to support children as students. Second, communicating: Design effective forms of school-to-home and home-to-school communications about school programs and children's progress. Third, volunteering: recruit and organize parent help and support. Fourth, learning at home: Provide information and ideas to families about how to help students at home with homework and other curriculum-related activities, decisions, and planning. Fifth, decision-making: include families as participants in school decisions and develop parent leaders and representatives. Furthermore, sixth, collaborating with the community: coordinate resources and services for families, students, and the school, and provide services to the community (Newman, 2019).

Similarly, the University of Minnesota (2018) shared its version of parental involvement models, including Model 1 — Independent - this model is based on the assumption that parents delegate to schools the responsibility for educating their children. Educators, in turn, accept the responsibility. Second, model 2 — Mission-driven - the school establishes the mission and enlists parents' support. The school identifies appropriate values and practices for children's success. Third, model 3 — Cooperative - the school recognizes families' expertise. The school assumes that interactions between home and school are helpful.

Fourth, model 4 — Collaborative - the schoolwork with families to accomplish a joint mission for children's educational success. There is a collaboration among parents, educators, and community members. Moreover, Hasler-Waters et al. (2018) discovered that the unique school environment made the intensity of parental involvement. Because parents were intimately aware of their children's needs and interests, they could use that knowledge to support their students. However, she also learned that these coaches faced significant challenges, including the shortage of time, the complexity of the role, and the need for immediate access to teachers.

Other than that, parents sometimes did not feel qualified to help students due to their unfamiliarity with the subject matter or when their students struggled with the content. This discovery underscores the findings made by Borup et al. (2013), who found a negative association with student outcomes when there was an over-reliance on parents for instructional support. While the parents in her study acknowledged that the educational management organization provided them with training or instructional tips, they needed to find these resources sufficient. Furthermore, the school could support families by communicating, being transparent with tools, and individualizing instruction. Students must be participating in and accountable for their learning. Parents should be available to monitor, mentor, and motivate students. She illustrated these themes in a model representing the interlocking connection between the themes (Curtis et al., 2015).

When parents and children collaborate in learning activities, bonding between parents and children increases to spend much more time together. Such instances allow parents to become a source of comfort in easing pain and worry and engage in conversations with their children to help alleviate their anxiety. It has been recommended that parents should be taught interventions on how to provide emotional support to children at times of uncertainty (Wang et al., 2020). Online schooling systems with parental support guidelines could help improve children's and their parents' bonds.

In summary, the related literature elaborated on the roles and strategies parents play in their children's development, how this affects their performance, and the experiences of parents acting as their children's study partners, challenges and coping mechanisms, learning opportunities, and insights. This related literature will offer adequate backing and a solid foundation for analyzing and extrapolating the study's

findings, further confirming its validity. This study was chosen because of many studies during a pandemic; the researcher focused on teachers and students, while this study concentrated on parents as conversational partners. Moreover, this study was conducted during the pandemic, when parents' roles were added due to many educational responsibilities. This study was presented in a qualitative method that focused on parents' experiences, especially those who have reached a lower level of education and served as study buddies of their children, making this study unique compared to the other studies.

Methodology

This section includes the research design, sampling design, conversational partners, role of the researcher, data sources, instrumentation, data gathering procedure, face-to-face interview, data analysis, the trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study employed a phenomenological qualitative research design. It is defined as an approach to research that seeks to describe the essence of a phenomenon by exploring it from the perspective of those who experienced it (Teherani et al., 2015). The phenomenological approach aims to illuminate the specific to identify phenomena through how the actors perceive them. This qualitative phenomenological research aimed to explore the lived experiences of parents who became the companions of their children in complying with Modular Learning activities. The lived experiences of the conversational partners were brought to light through these conversations. The conversations were focused on presenting their ideas, thoughts, and experiences they have felt, lived, and going through

Sampling Design

This study utilized purposive sampling to emphasize specific people relevant to the research and capable of answering the research questions. Purposive sampling is described by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012) as a technique in which the researcher depends on their findings when selecting a method. It follows when essentials are carefully chosen for the sample selected by the researcher's decision. The main objective of the purposive sampling design is to explore the parents' life experiences as their children's study buddies during the implementation of the Modular Learning

Program.

Conversational Partners

The study's conversational partners are 16 parents with at least two children enrolled in school. The selection of conversational partners was based on the following inclusion criteria, which are: (a) must be parents of at least two students enrolled for School Year 2021-2022; (b) 25-60 years old; and (c) unable to finish an elementary level. Those who did not meet the criteria were excluded as CPs of this study.

Role of the Researcher

In this study, the diverse lived experiences and feelings of the conversational partners were noted. The researcher is a provider of transparent and understandable questions and is a listener to the conversational partners' narration of their lived experiences and reactions, challenges encountered, coping strategies, and aspirations for their selves and their children. Further, the researcher explained the study and its purpose without bias to the conversational partners. In the interview proper, the researcher served as the interviewer who appropriately conducted interviews according to the procedure and followed the interview guide. The researcher observed the conversational partners' responses, understanding their human experiences. The researcher's data were collected and transcribed to ensure truthful information. The researcher also ensured to safeguard of the conversational partners' identities. Lastly, the researcher was an analyzer and interpreter of the data congruent with what the conversational partners said during the in-depth interview. Specifically, the researcher's roles include being an encoder, transcriber, translator, interpreter, and analyzer of data based on the responses of the conversational partners.

Data Sources

Every research was based on data, analyzed, and interpreted to get the correct information. In this phenomenological research, the conversational partners responded to the interview guide from which the primary data were derived. This way, data interpretation was better, and targeted issues were addressed. The secondary data were gathered from published, printed sources, including literature, surveys, and compilations from computerized databases and information systems (Cook, 2011).

Instrumentation

This study utilized a semi-structured interview guide to gather the needed data, which served as an instrument. It was divided into three parts. Part I contains the conversational partners' orientation for them to become aware of the interview flow. Part II is the interview proper, which contains preliminary questions to set the mood of the conversational partners, followed by the leading questions comprising 12 items that determined their lived experiences, their struggles, and the challenges they encountered, how they cope, as well as their aspirations. Last is the wrap-up question to conclude the interview.

Data Gathering Procedure

To facilitate this study, the researcher considered the following steps. Primarily, the researcher sought approval from the Dean of the Graduate School of Notre Dame of Midsayap College to conduct a research study. Secondly, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd Cotabato Division by sending a letter duly noted by the Dean of the Graduate School of Notre Dame of Midsayap College to request approval for the interview of the conversational partners, then submitted a copy of this letter to the school heads and conversational partners to enable the researcher to conduct the study.

Then, the researcher personally communicated with the conversational partners for their approval before conducting the in-depth interview and explained to them comprehensively the content of the informed consent. The conversational partners accepted the invitation positively and willingly by affixing their signatures to the consent form. After the in-depth interview, the researcher transcribed all the data gathered and translated all the information into English. Finally, the researcher let the conversational partners read all the transcribed and translated information they gave. To check the congruency of data to their statement, the conversational partners affixed their signatures to the verification form.

Results

This section presents the qualitative analysis outcome of the research questions answers. The results are presented based on emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

Profile of the Conversational Partners

The conversational partners of this study are primarily

female, and they expressed their life experiences about their parental involvement as buddies in Modular Learning Program implemented for their children. The expressed ideas by conversational partners were used to sort out the insights related to the salient results of their lived experiences as study buddies of their children studying in a modular set-up. Matrix 1 presents the conversational partners' profiles.

Matrix 1. Profile of the Conversational Partners

Code Number	Age	Gender	Educational Attainment
JCG-P01	49	Female	Grade 6
JCG-P02	43	Female	Have not Gone to School
JCG-P03	41	Female	Grade 4
JCG-P04	62	Female	Have not Gone to School
JCG-P05	44	Female	Have not Gone to School
JCG-P06	37	Female	Grade 5
JCG-P07	33	Male	Grade 6
JCG-P08	46	Male	Grade 6
JCG-P09	43	Female	Have not Gone to School
JCG-P10	47	Female	Have not Gone to School
JCG-P11	65	Female	Have not Gone to School
JCG-P12	47	Female	Grade 3
JCG-P13	65	Male	Grade 3
JCG-P14	62	Female	Have not Gone to School
JCG-P15	48	Male	Grade 6
JCG-P16	45	Female	Have not Gone to School

The first conversational partner was JCG-P01. She is a female, 49 years old, and her educational attainment is up to grade 6 only. A significant experience she talked about was that she was happy when she became a study buddy of her children saying, "I am happy to be a part of my children's education because my son learns from his study."

The second conversational partner was JCG-PO2, who has not gone to school; she shared her feeling of happiness even if they encountered good and bad experiences as a buddy of her child "I am happy that I become a study buddy of my children, especially this time of pandemic because I am allowed to learn new things just for example how to write, the negative experience is since I was not able to attend school, I have a hard time in dealing with my students since I could not explain to them the content of their modules."

The third conversational partner was JCG-PO3, female, 41 years old, and finished Grade 4. She stated that as a study buddy of her children, she felt happy because she became part of the study of her children. According to her, "I am happy. After all, even during the pandemic, my children could study."

The fourth conversational partner was JCG-PO4, 62 years old and has never attended school. She is the type of mother and grandmother who is caring and loving. Even though she could not attend school, she is constantly extending help to her children in different ways. However, there are times when she finds difficulty in assessing her children, especially in answering their modules "There is a time when I have difficulty with my grandson's study, especially in answering modules because I do not know it since I have not studied anything, and I cannot read and understand the lesson."

She also said that she is happy being part of the study of her children and grandchildren. In that way, she was able to perform parental duties and responsibilities. "I am delighted because somehow, I am helping them with their studies. Moreover, I see that my children have a bright future because they are persistent and interested in their education."

The fifth conversational partner is JCG-PO5. She is now 44 years old and has not gone to school. She is the kind of mother that is very supportive of her children, especially their education. "I supported them and provided for their needs. Especially during the time that they are answering their modules."

The sixth conversational partner is JCG-PO7, a 33-year-old male who reached Grade 6. He shared that he was happy that his children learned from Modular Learning Program and did not stop their studies, especially at a time when the guidance of a mother is very needed in the study of the children. She said, "I am happy to be part of my children learning something in their studies; even if it was just a modular, they still learned something, and their studies did not stop."

The seventh conversational partner is JCG-PO7. He is a 33-year-old male who completed his grade 6. He shared that he is happy that the children learned something in their studies, even using modules. He said, "I am happy because the children learned something in their studies; even if it was just a modular, they still learned something, and their studies did not stop."

The eighth conversational partner JCG-PO8 is a male who shared that parents need to be happy even during a pandemic because they need to be happy to be part of the children's education. "We cannot do anything, so we must be happy even during the pandemic. We are just happy to be part of our children's education."

The ninth conversational partner is JCG-PO9. She shared that even if she has not attended school, she is happy to be part of her children's education. According to her, "Yes, I am happy to be a part of my children's education. I am happy because they learned to read so that people would not make fun of them. Furthermore, if I die, I will be complacent because I know that they can face it since they have learned a lot in their studies, and I know this will be their weapon in their daily quest in life. I am also happy because they now know that people will no longer mock them and tell them hurtful words."

The tenth conversational partner is JCG-PO10, who shared that she is happy even if the children are just at home; they continue to study and learn, and they were not the only ones who learned, but the parents also learned, which makes her happy, for they learned something in their education. "Yes, I am happy. Even if they are just at home, they continue to study and learn. They were not the only ones who learned, but we both learned, which makes me happy because they learned something in their studies."

The eleventh conversational partner is JCG-P11. She shared that she was happy to be part of her children's education because, despite the pandemic, they continue their education to have a good job after graduation. "Yes, I am happy to be a part of my children's education because, despite the pandemic, they were able to continue their education so that they can have a good job after they graduate from their studies."

The twelfth conversational partner is JCG-P12, who shared that she felt happy to be a part of her children's education because they increased their knowledge and experiences" Yes, I am happy that I have been a part of my children's education. I am happy because they increase their knowledge and their experiences."

The thirteenth conversational partner is JCG-P13, who shared that he was happy to be a part of his children's education but noticed a modular approach to education that kids did not learn anything "I am also happy because I became part of my children's education. However, I noticed that in the modular education approach."

The fourteenth conversational partner JCG-P14 shared that she was happy that the children are in education so they can finish schooling and find a good job one day; all of that is for the betterment of their lives in the future. "Of course, I am happy. So that they can finish school and find a good job one day, and all of that is for the betterment of their lives in the future."

The fifteenth conversational partner is PCG-P14, who shared that he was happy to provide his children an opportunity to learn "I am happy because I want my children to learn."

Lastly, the sixteenth conversational partner is a JCG-P16 female who has not gone to school. She shared that she was happy to be part of her children's education even though she has not attended school but availed an opportunity to guide her children in their studies.

"I am happy that I became a part of my children's education. Even though I have not attended school, I still have the opportunity to guide my children in their studies."

Categorizing of Emergent Themes

After the in-depth interviews, the audio-recorded exchanges were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. A cross-analysis in comparing the core ideas was used to present information. This was adopted after the guide written by Hill, Thompson, and Williams (1997) entitled, *A Guide to Conducting Consensual Qualitative Research*, which used the three classifications of responses: general, typical, and variant.

The first category is General, meaning the core idea applies to all cases (16 cases). Next is Typical, meaning the idea applies to half or more cases (8-15 cases). Lastly, the variant applies to less than half to at least two cases (2-7 cases) (cited by Goodrich et al., 2019).

In categorizing the information, the themes were presented by the research question and referred to as major themes. Under the major themes are the core ideas from the responses of the CPs. Another column

was included in the table showing the frequency of the responses, which became the basis for the categorization.

Themes

There were 180 significant statements and 12 core ideas framed in the thematic analysis. Matrix 2 shows four major themes and 12 core ideas that emerged from the subjective experiences of the conversational partners, specifically their lived experiences on their role in implementing the modular learning program for their children's education. The core ideas and categorization were presented, and each major theme was discussed.

Matrix 2. Themes, Core Ideas, and Categorization of the Role of Parents in Implementation of Modular Learning Program

MAJOR THEMES	CORE IDEAS	CATEGORIZATION
Learning Experiences	Sense of happiness for involvement in student's learning	Typical
	Opportunity to learn new things together	Typical
	Able to perform parental duties and responsibilities	Typical
Hurdles encountered	Children's appreciation of parent's effort	General
	Limited knowledge due to educational background	Typical
	Different household activities	General
	The emotional state of giving up	Variant
Conquering Difficulties	Setting priorities through appropriate planning	Variant
	Praying for God's guidance	Variant
Insights and Realizations	Unity and cooperation among the family members	Typical
	Valuing education	Typical
	Importance of proper time management	Typical

The themes that emerged from the in-depth interviews are presented: learning experiences, hurdles encountered, conquering difficulties, and insights and realizations.

Learning Experiences

The core ideas on Learning Experiences that categorize the major theme are presented in Matrix 3. These are extracted from the CPs' responses to their lived experiences as study buddies in the modular learning program of their children.

It is shown that Learning Experiences as the first major theme with the core ideas: a sense of happiness for involvement in students' learning, the opportunity to learn new things together, the ability to perform parental duties and responsibilities, and children's appreciation of parents' effort.

Matrix 3. Theme 1, Core Ideas and Categorization

MAJOR THEME	CORE IDEAS	CATEGORIZATION
Learning Experiences	Sense of happiness for involvement in student's learning	Typical
	Opportunity to learn new things together	Typical
	Able to perform parental duties and responsibilities	Typical
	Children's appreciation of parent's effort	General

Sense of Happiness for Involvement in Student's Learning

The core idea was developed from the significant statements shared by the conversational partners. Parents feel happy when they get involved in their children's learning using the modular learning program. As the conversational partners mentioned, they give the children academic assistance in answering their modules. The Conversational Partners stated that despite the pandemic, they were able to assist their children.

"I am happy because even though there was a pandemic, they were able to study because of the module." (JCG-P02)

"It is also pretty fun even though it is a pandemic; they were able to study, then I also learned something." (JCG-P03).

Parents who were cooperative partners added that they were happy because their children also showed happiness when they were helped to know the answer to their module. This resulted in their willingness to help with household chores.

"I saw their joy and enthusiasm because, somehow, I help them, and because of that, they thank me for

helping them." (JCG-P01)

"I can see that they were happy every time I help them, and in return, they are thankful to me." (JCG-P13)

"They are happy and thanking me for helping them, and in return, they helped in the household chores." (JCG-P07)

"Happy that I help them ... Their joy is evident when they join me in answering their modules." (JCG-P10)

"I noticed in them that they were happy... They thank me because I help them." (JCG-P12)

"They are happy that I am helping them; they said thank you, Mama, for all your sacrifices and in helping us always." (JCG-P14)

"I am happy. I see in them that they are happy when I help them and tell them to answer their module, and consequently, they help with household chores." (JCG-P01)

Some conversational partners emphasized that they were happy that their children were happy when being helped by parents and were exhibiting a positive desire to learn; children are happy being taught by parents even if their parents have only reached a lower level of education despite that they are still happy because they believe that their efforts were going toward building a better future for their children.

I notice in them that they were happy... They thank me because I help them." (JCG-P12)

"They are happy that I am helping them; they said thank you, Mama, for all your sacrifices and in helping us always." (JCG-P14)

"I am happy. I see in them that they are happy when I help them and tell them to answer their module, and consequently, they help with household chores." (JCG-P01)

"I am delighted because somehow, I am helping them with their studies. Moreover, my children have a bright future because they are persistent and interested in their education. Even if they walk as long as they can study." (JCG-P05)

"Yes, I am happy because I helped them answer their modules.

They ask me if they do not know how to answer their

modules, and I teach or help them to answer. Furthermore, If I do not know, I will do the research." (JCG-P06)

"I am happy, sir, because he follows what I say. Even if I could not attend school When I told him to go to their sister and let her teach him, he immediately followed me and all my advice, so I was happy." (JCG-P09)

"I am happy, sir, because it is for the good of my child. And as a parent, I am happy to help and be a part of my children's learning." (JCG-P10)

"I am happy, sir, because my children are learning more. So as a mother, it is very happy to feel that you see your children learn something because it is also for them when the day comes." (JCG-P11)

"I am happy, sir, because I help them with their modules. When there are questions they do not know to answer, I teach them. I explain to them the best that I can how to answer the questions." (JCG-P12)

The core idea of a sense of happiness for involvement in students' learning is classified as Typical since 13 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Opportunity to Learn New Things Together

The conversational partners indicated that their children learned something even if they used the learning modules. As part of children's learning at home, parents had the opportunity to learn new things with their children. The following are the CPs' responses:

"I am happy because my son learned something from their studies." (JCG-P01)

"I am happy because they learn in their studies, and I help them in their studies." (JCG-P05)

"I am happy, Because the children learned something in their studies, even if it was just a modular, they still learned something, and their studies did not stop." (JCG-P07)

"I am happy. Even if they are just at home, they continue to study and learn. They were not the only ones who learned, but we both learned, which makes me happy, for they learned something in their studies." (JCG-P10)

"Yes, I am happy to be a part of my children's

education because, despite the pandemic, they were able to continue their education so that they can have a good job after they graduate from their studies." (JCG-P11)

"I am delighted, sir, that I have been a part of my children's education. I am happy because they increase their knowledge and their experiences." (JCG-P12)

"I am happy because I want my children to learn." (JCG-P15)

"I am happy, sir, that I became a part of my children's education. Even though I have not attended school, I still have the opportunity to guide my children in their studies." (JCG-P16)

"My children already know, and they can help me because they already know." (JCG-P02)

The core idea of the opportunity to learn new things together is classified as Typical since 11 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Able to Perform Parental Duties and Responsibilities

While assisting their children with their learning modules, the conversational partners still perform their parental duties and responsibilities to their respective families. The CPs had exhibited their role as parents and responsibilities at home that cannot be left behind. The CPs shared that their duties and responsibilities are done in the:

In their studies and attending meetings. (JCG-P02)

In their study, when they have work, I help them so that they can pass their modules at the right time. They can join the chat and pass the projects on the messenger by providing the load. Even though it is challenging to find a way for them to participate just for their education. (JCG-P03)

In their studies, I supported them and provided for their needs. Especially during the time, they are answering their modules. (JCG-P05)

In their needs and their studies, sir, because I gave them money so that they can buy load for their cellphone so that they can use it to answer their modules. When I advise them to fix their module answering because it is also for them. (JCG-P06)

In my child's education, in answering their module. I am the one who gets his module in school and with the

costs of his studies. (JCG-P09)

In my son's studies, sir. I always remind them to study hard and answer the modules because it is also for them. I told him that to understand formal education; he would learn something in English and Arabic for the same reason. (JCG-P10)

In my son's education. I took their modules to school. Moreover, sometimes they are the ones I get. I told them to take the modules to continue their studies. (JCG-P11)

In their study. I tell them to take their modules to school and when they can answer them so they can continue to learn and have a promising future one day. (JCG-P12)

In the education of our children. In answering their modules and their learning needs. (JCG-P13)

In my children's education. By giving a reminder to answer their modules (JCG-P14)

In their study. I take care of them and always tell them to answer their modules because that is the study method today. After all, we are still in a pandemic. (JCG-P16)

In the module, whenever their modules arrive, I always tell them that you children, complete all the modules so that you can return them immediately on time and you will be able to get a new one so that you can efficiently finish your studies. I reminded them not to waste their time because it looks like you are still in school and studying. (JCG-P07)

The core idea of being able to perform parental duties and responsibilities is classified as Typical since 11 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Children's Appreciation of Parent's Efforts

Children recognize the efforts of their parents in helping them accomplish their learning modules. The CPs shared that the children exhibited a feeling of appreciation for the efforts exerted by parents to assist them in their modular learning. The following are the CPs shared statements:

They are happy every time I help them. I can see on their faces that they always smile and say. Thank you, Mother, for helping us, and in return, they also help me with their help; they also help me with household chores. (JCG-P05)

They thank me because I help them (JCG-P06)

They are happy, sir, when I help them. They always smile at me and tell me, " Father, Thank you! (JCG-P15)

The core idea of children's appreciation of parents' efforts is classified as General since all 16 of the 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Hurdles Encountered

The core ideas and categorization of the theme Hurdles Encountered are presented in Matrix 4. These are extracted from the CPs' responses to the challenges they encountered.

In Matrix 4, the Hurdles Encountered as the second major theme is shown. Hurdles encountered are presented in three core ideas: Limited knowledge due to educational background, Different household activities, and Emotional state of giving up.

Matrix 4. *Theme 2, Core Ideas and Categorization*

MAJOR THEME	CORE IDEAS	CATEGORIZATION
Hurdles encountered	Limited knowledge due to educational background	Typical
	Different household activities	General
	The emotional state of giving up	General

Limited knowledge due to educational background

The core idea of limited knowledge due to educational background was formulated from the significant statements by the conversational partners. This means that parents made many adjustments in assisting their children with their learning modules because of their limited knowledge due to educational attainment. The CPs had expressed their feeling of acquiring limited knowledge in education that hindered their capacity to assist their children. The CPs indicated that:

We cannot do anything, sir; that is why we must be happy, even during a pandemic. I am happy to be a part of my children's education even though I have limited knowledge about their lessons. (JCG-P08)

I am also happy because I became part of my children's education. However, I noticed that in the Modular approach to education, the kids did not learn anything, and I could not give or teach them

everything since I had only limited ideas on the lesson. (JCG-P13).

I also find it difficult... I do not know their lessons, so I have a hard time because I studied less... Their lesson is different now compared to what I studied before. (JCG-P01)

It is difficult for me to understand... I also have a hard time comprehending their lessons. (JCG-P06)

I am confused... I have difficulty with the lessons in the module (JCG-P07)

I am also having a hard time with the subject content, and sometimes I do not understand, but because we work together, we eventually Solve those problems. (JCG-P10)

It is hard for me to understand the contents of the module (JCG-P11)

There are also times when I have difficulty analyzing the content of the modules. (JCG-P12)

I could not teach them everything since I had only limited ideas and knowledge of their lesson, and besides that, their topics were quite different from what I had studied before. (JCG-P13)

Sometimes I have difficulty with the content of their modules because it is different from what I went through before. (JCG-P15)

The core idea of limited knowledge due to educational background is classified as Typical since 14 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Different Household Activities

The core idea of different household activities was formulated based on the significant statements expressed by the conversational partners. There are many concerns the parents had to attend to aside from helping their children in their learning modules. The CPs indicated their expressions on the effect of different household activities on the chance to assist their children in answering their modules. CPs expressed that:

There is time for answering modules. It usually falls around 10 PM, and there is also a time for work and household chores. I balance it Well so that I can fulfill my duties (JCG-P01)

I balanced my work at home and helping my children.

I prioritize household chores before helping my children (JCG-P02)

In the morning, all I would do was do the selling of my goods. Then in the evening, around 9 o'clock, that was my time for them, and I taught them about their modules (JCG-P03)

I balance my time in the morning before I go to work (JCG-P04)

What comes first to the problem is the first if the solution is given, whether it is a problem at home or school (JCG-P05)

Planning and scheduling what work should be prioritized (JCG-P06)

When I have a job on the farm, I leave my children to my older son so that he can teach and supervise in answering their modules so that even if I am not around, they will continue answering their modules so that they will not be late during submission. I will teach them in their module when I finish my work, especially at night. (JCG-P07)

I told them to work hard and, if they know, answer, I will do the farm work first ... if I am done doing the farm work, that is when I help my children with their modules. (JCG-P08)

Prioritize housework while my children answer their modules. When I am done with homework, I watch them answering their modules (JCG-P11)

When I do not have a job, I help them with their modules (JCG-CP12)

I put housework first. I will help my grandchildren with their modules when I finish my household chores. (JCG-P14)

I prioritize the housework in the morning, and when I have a vacancy, that is the time when I s extend help with my children's modules (JCG-P15)

The core idea different household activities is classified as General since 16 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Emotional State of Giving Up

According to the conversational partners, they feel sad seeing their children having difficulty answering the modules. Parents also find it difficult because they cannot understand the content. Others gave up on

helping their children because of some concerns, while others, despite the difficulty, still worked with their children. The CPs indicated that the emotional challenges encountered resulted in the feeling of giving up. The CPs indicated that:

Yes, sometimes they fight each other because the older brother will not help his younger brother, and I am tired of household chores. Once I got to the point where I almost gave up helping them because I was tired. (JCG-P01)

Sometimes come to the point of giving up, especially when I do not know their lessons. (JCG-P03)

Sometimes I feel tired and about to give up because I always have a lot of work every day. (JCG-P07)

Yes, sir, because I had a hard time comprehending their lessons, and it came to the point that I was about to give up. (JCG-P08) Yes, I have come to the point that I am about to give up because I am uneducated, and It is quite difficult for me to assist them in their modules. (JCG-P09)

I am having a hard time, sir, because I have not studied anything, so it is hard for me to understand the module's contents... I feel sad because I cannot answer them. (JCG-P09 & JCG-P10)

Sometimes when I am tired and because I am old and uneducated. (JCG-P11)

Yes, because children need to improve in this style of education. I also need more skills to help them with their studies. It would have been better for a teacher to teach them face-to-face because the teachers could adequately explain the content of the modules. (JCG-P12)

Yes, sir, because teaching is difficult because they are even more educated than us. Sometimes we also need help finding an answer because we did not go through the lessons while studying, and I did not go through modular learning before. (JCG-P13)

Yes, sir, when I am tired from work or housework, especially since I care for two houses. However, when I am feeling okay and able to relax, I continue to take care of my grandson's modules. Even simple guidance and telling them to answer their modules is a big help so that they pay attention to their studies. (JCG-P14)

Yes, sir, I had a problem related to daily needs at the time. I tell them to answer their modules for I have to solve my problems first. (JCG-P15)

Sometimes, especially when I am busy with my work (JCG-P16)

The core idea Emotional state of giving up is classified as General since all conversational partners articulated this answer.

Conquering Difficulties

The core ideas and categorization of the theme Conquering Difficulties are shown in Matrix 5. These are extracted from the CPs responses. Matrix 5 presents how they conquered difficulties.

The Matrix shows Conquering Difficulties as the third major theme. Conquering Difficulties presents three core ideas setting priorities through appropriate learning, praying for God's guidance, and unity and cooperation among the family members.

Matrix 5. Theme 3, Core Ideas and Categorization

MAJOR THEME	CORE IDEAS	CATEGORIZATION
Conquering Difficulties	Setting priorities through appropriate learning	Variant
	Praying for God's guidance	Variant
	Unity and cooperation among the family members	Variant

Figure 7. .

Setting Priorities through Appropriate Learning

The core idea of setting priorities through appropriate learning was formulated from the significant statements expressed by the conversational partners. Having faced difficulties in the modular program, they were able to look at some ways to cope with those challenges. The CPs indicated that problem categorization, coping and facing challenges, finding solutions to the problem, setting priorities, and balancing time helped them acquire appropriate learning. The CPs indicated that:

I was able to cope and face it with courage. Looking for a way to cope with those challenges, I had a hard time helping answer their modules, but everything was okay because we were together. (JCG-P03)

I endured for my grandson's future. Even though I am having a hard time because I am the only one who helps him even though I could not attend school. (JCG-P04)

They were able to continue their education despite the pandemic, secondly is that they know how to clean, and then they joyfully help me with household chores. Lastly, we have time to bond with each other as we answer their modules. (JCG-P05)

I bravely face it, even if it is complicated. Most importantly, I prioritized things to be given immediate attention, and I was able to look for a solution to address those problems. (JCG-P08)

Identifying which tasks are urgent makes it a priority and balances time because you also need to work hard for the family, and you also need time for the children with their studies. (JCG-P09)

I am looking for a solution to the problems that need to be addressed, like what I have gone through. (JCG-P12)

The core idea setting priorities through appropriate learning is classified as variant since 7 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Praying for God's Guidance

Praying to God and asking for guidance and strength to overcome the challenges was the positive coping mechanism of parents. The CP indicated that their relationship with God was strengthened, providing them with guidance and strength to face trials.

Always work hard and pray to Allah (JCG-P04)

I ask Allah for guidance and help to guide my family and me through the trials we will face. (JCG-P09)

I am asking for the help of the Lord to guide my children (JCG-P11)

I cope and balance them. Praying to Allah give me the strength to overcome trials. (JCG-P14)

I ask for the Lord's guidance to guide my actions and cope with the trials I will face. (JCG-P15)

I extend my patience and ask Allah for guidance (JCG-P16)

The core idea of praying for God's guidance is classified as Variant since 6 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Unity and Cooperation within the Family Members

A harmonious relationship with the family members is

vital to supporting children struggling with learning modules. Their involvement would mean they had shown concern, unity, and cooperation with their children's education. However, there were instances when they sought help from their neighbors and children's classmates. The CPs exerted their effort to help their children and develop connections and bonds with other members of the family who exhibited cooperation and oneness. According to them:

We are just working together with my son (JCG-P03). No, we-we are the only ones answering the modules because I do not have anyone to ask for help, and no one else helps him but me and Allah. (CP4)

There with my eldest son, sir, because he is smart and intelligent. (JCG-P6) The cooperation and oneness of everyone leads in answering their modules. (JCG-P08.)

We strengthened our relationship as a family, and we had time to bond. (JCG-P07)

We work with my eldest son to answer his younger sibling's module. (JCG-P15)

We work hand in hand with my older son and daughter in answering their modules. (JCG-P16)

To my grandson's brother and his father, The oneness and unity of our family. (JCG-P14)

I am asking the help of my eldest daughter since she has higher educational attainment. (JCG-P01)

We work with my son and daughter to answer their younger siblings' modules. (JCG-P11)

Even though I have not studied anything, when it comes to module content, I do not have a hard time because whenever my grandson asks me something, his father is there to help me. He is the one who will help my grandson. (JCG-P09)

The core idea Harmonious relationship with family members is classified as Typical since 14 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Insights and Realizations

The core ideas and categorization of the theme Insights and Realizations are presented in Matrix 6. These are extracted from the CPs' responses as to what they have learned when they become their children's study buddies. This theme presents two core ideas: the valuing education and the importance of proper time management.

Matrix 6. Theme 4, Core Ideas and Categorization

MAJOR THEME	CORE IDEAS	CATEGORIZATION
Insights and Realizations	Valuing Education	Typical
	Importance of proper time management	Variant

Valuing Education

through the challenges of modular learning, parents got insights and realizations that parents and children should value education. The CPs had indicated their value of education since some had limited education. CPs indicated that they also learn some lessons when they assist their children. Others learned to read and write and be updated with the current contents of the lesson. They stated that:

When I learn even a little of my children's lessons, it will be the best thing to happen to me as a study buddy for my children. (JCG-P01)

I learned to write, read at least a little (JCG-P02), and much more. In other words, we both learned. (JCG-P3).

We both learned and realized the value of education. (JCG-P07)

My grandson's learning was my great experience as a partner in his studies. (JCG-P04)

I also learned a little bit, especially since I could not study. I learned to appreciate. I try to learn their lesson, too, to help them. (JCG-P05)

When ma'am taught me to write my name at school, even though my hand was shaking while writing, I am very thankful for the learning imparted to my child and me. (JCG-P09)

I also learned at least a little. We are both learning now with my son. (JCG-P10)

I learned the essence of valuing education (JCG-P11), the value of education (JCG-P12), to value education and the proper guidance of our children. (JCH-P16)

To value knowledge because, in this situation, the

lessons we forget are gradually revived. If anything, we also learned simultaneously as our children learned. (JCG-P13)

I also learned something daily with my grandson, who is answering his modules. (JCG-P14)

I learned at least a little at the same time as my children learned during the pandemic. (JCG-P15)

The core idea Valuing education is classified as Typical since 14 out of 16 conversational partners articulated this answer.

Importance of Proper Time Management

Time management can efficiently manage one's time in a way that helps one finish the required tasks. Parents find some time to help their children answer the learning modules. The CPs indicated that they tried to find time to assist their children. The CPs said that they budget their time to help their children.

I worked out a way to budget my time at work and helped my children answer their modules. It is just a matter of sacrifice. (JCG-P01)

I finish my chores here at home first or prioritize the housework before I take care of them and help them. (JCG-P02)

As for time management, I am fine with time because I have enough time for my grandson to study. All I need is time budgeting. I clean in the morning; then I help her every night. (JCG-P04)

I plan everything I do and which ones to prioritize. (JCG-P05)

What I do is budget my time with them. (JCG-P07)

I am sure to budget my time. There is a time for household chores and time for helping my son and daughter answer their modules. (JCG-P08)

I am fine since I manage to budget my time properly, and we have much time at night to do his modules. (JCG-P09)

We are looking for a way to balance the time to get through the trials I have experienced. (JCG-P13)

I had no problem because I was planning and budgeting my time and had time to help them. (JCG-P15)

I do not have a problem with time management

because I have much time for my children to guide them, especially in their modules. (JCG-P16)

There are some difficulties encountered due to the limited knowledge of parents due to their low level of education. Based on the statement of CP:

There is a time when I need help with my grandson's studies, especially in answering his modules, because I do not know it because I have not studied anything, and I cannot read and understand the lesson. (CP3)

The core idea Importance of proper time management is classified as a Variant since 9 out of 16 conversational partners articulated the answer.

Discussion

This provides discussion of the themes from the analyzed data. This aimed to explore the parents' lived experiences as study buddies of their children using the learning modules. It examined their experiences, challenges, coping mechanism, and learnings. A Modular Learning Program was implemented as an alternative strategy during the Pandemic. The study utilized the qualitative study to gather data from parents as buddies in complying with modular learning activities of students.

Based on the concept of Bhandari (2020), qualitative research is used to understand how people experience the world. They share some similarities but emphasize different aims and perspectives. As such, in-depth interviews were conducted with the conversational partners to provide a clear view of the significant lived experiences of the parents. The conversational partners of the study were 16 parents who spontaneously shared their experiences and described their stories. The narratives were analyzed and categorized into themes and core ideas. The main themes of the study are presented as follows.

Learning Experiences

From the experiences of the conversational partners on the role of parents as study buddies in the implementation of the Modular Learning Program, the essential theme of Learning Experiences emerged. Parents extend the time and support their children. They believe that the way the school encourages them to participate in their children's education. Even though it is challenging since it is the first time to implement the Modular Learning Program, the parents still see and perceive its brighter side, providing

sufficient time to oversee their children in their studies. They spare time for their children and assist them in their studies. They are also given a chance to share their knowledge and skills with their children and with an offered avenue for them to show how they care about their children (Paco et al., 2021).

Learning experiences include the fundamental concepts of being happy to participate in students' education, having the chance to learn new things together, being able to carry out parental obligations and responsibilities, and children appreciating their parents' efforts. The parents' learning experiences are distinctive in that they have witnessed the beneficial effects of implementation in fostering harmonious relationships with their kids. They think no one else would sacrifice themselves for their kids. Therefore, they must fulfill their duties and obligations as parents and study partners at home (Milles, 2020). The fact that each and every CP had something to say on how they have dealt with stress is evidence in favor of this study.

The sense of happiness for involvement in student learning was experienced by 14 conversational partners. The parents who served as buddies in the modular learning program exhibited happiness in assisting their children to complete the modular answers to show good academic performance, which indicates the parents' typical roles of teaching, guiding, and raising children to become vital members of their communities. This means that parents are highly engaged in modular learning. They are highly preoccupied with supporting and managing their children's modular learning. Despite the inevitable challenges, parents feel happier and more involved in having more time with their children's education.

This implies that parent's guidance and support will inspire the children to study. This implies also that Parents as buddies are exhibiting happiness and excitement in assisting their children in Modular Learning to meet the educational requirements. The exhibited efforts of parents are appreciated by children when they help in improving the bond between children and their parents. This Study is supported by the study of (Wang, Zhang, Zhao, Zhang, & Jiang, 2020) stated that during pandemic, DepEd used the Alternate Learning Program of Modules to teach pupils. Conversational partners expressed their joy when assisting their children in answering the modules. The study's findings indicate that parents and children's cooperation in learning educational activities are intended to strengthen the appreciation of children on the exerted efforts of parents, and it has been

recommended that parents be taught interventions on how to provide emotional support to children in times of uncertainty.

This study is further supported by the study of the Philippine Information Agency (2020) study, that the youngsters will be motivated to learn by their parents' advice and support. This is also supported by the study of Colombo (2006), reality revealed that in educational set-ups in terms of modular distance learning, the participation of parents is the missing link in equity. However, it is indicated that schools and teachers cannot simply educate every child independently because these children need emotional support from parents and family.

Parents expressed that they had the opportunity to learn new things while helping their children answer the learning modules. Parents have discovered a new outlet for learning new topics as part of their children's home learning. During this period, it also serves as a means for parents to master new skills. It is clear, not only children but also parents are learning new skills. This is a fantastic opportunity for parents since they are given the opportunity and chance to learn new things that their children and parents may apply in their daily lives. This means that this core idea of learning experiences indicated that Modular Learning Program entails the learners staying at home, and this has become a challenging routine for the parents since they are the ones who will be teaching their child just to ensure their child's education.

The implication of the findings indicates that in Modular Learning as a strategy of distance learning, the learners stay at home, and parents try their best to support their children, especially on the concepts of the modules that are quite complicated. This experience affirms the statement of Manlangit et al. (2020) that distance learning necessitates the parents to study with their child for a better learning outcome. They serve as home facilitators and para-teachers who facilitate and guide the students in answering the modular lessons they sent during the modular learning. In addition, Luaña (2021) the studies exhibited support to the parents and children in complying with the modular learning program requirements as they learn new things together and enumerated suggestions on ways how parents can guide their children in answering modules: guiding by explaining, giving examples, correcting their children's incorrect answers, guiding by 'Googling' the answer, and guiding by directly giving the correct answers. The attachment expands when parents and children work together on educational activities since they can spend more time

around each other. This attachment allows parents to perform parental duties and responsibilities and become a source of comfort in easing pain and worry and engage in conversations with their children to help alleviate their anxiety. Parents should be competent to provide emotional support to children at times of uncertainty.

This indicates that parental duty begins with the child's formal enrollment in school and continues throughout the educational process. Parents should collaborate with administrators, instructors, and educational authorities, as well as actively participate in the process of constructing educational programs for their children. The physical care of the child is the responsibility of the parents, as is raising the child in a safe and non-violent manner. Parents are responsible for the physical care of their children, as well as ensuring that they are reared in a safe and non-violent environment. Teachers are responsible for issues relating to class and student activities, student needs, instructional materials, expectations, and obligations. If there is an issue with the child's education or the school itself, they should be told by the school administration or the instructor since parents play a very vital, critical, and key part in their children's education. As a result, they must carry out their duties. This finding implies that parents' involvement as a buddy in their children's education have a greater chance of succeeding in school and achieving of educational development.

This supports the statement of Garbe et al. (2020), which emphasized that parents struggle to balance their work, home, and teaching responsibilities. In the long run, the parents were able to adjust to the situation, and they were able to handle the situation to perform their duties and responsibilities to their children. In the current pandemic situation, parental roles can help establish a pleasant learning environment for their children. The ability of parents to play many roles at home is critical to maintaining a positive learning environment for their children (Ratih et al., 2021).

Children's appreciation of parent's efforts academically prove that parents intend to develop their children for a better future. The parents and children collaborate in learning activities, and bonding between parents and children increases to spend much more time together. Such instances allow parents to become a source of comfort in easing pain and worry and engage in conversations with their children to help alleviate their anxiety.

This means that children appreciated the efforts of their parents, who were helping them answer their learning modules. This finding implies that parents' effort serves as the major component of the educational accomplishment of their children in the Modular Learning program. It further implies that the parents' effort in their children's education is exhibited by their assistance with the educational requirements on Modular Learning. The learning experiences of the parents and children exhibited a sense of happiness for the assistance of parents in educational learning. This scenario provided an opportunity for parents and children to learn new things.

This result supports the statement of Kim (2020) that parental engagement is a critical factor influencing student achievement. Castro et al. (2015) added that parental engagement is the active participation of parents in all aspects of their children's social, emotional, and academic development. This also supports the statement of Borup et al. (2015); Keaton and Gilbert (2020) that the level of involvement changes due to the parents' abilities and expectations, differing student needs, and shared responsibility with teachers. This indicates a positive concept in support of the expressed statement of McCartney (2022) which emphasized that children express how grateful they are to their parents for their love and sacrifices and sometimes are more in complying with their modular requirements. Simple words of thank messages that come right from the heart are after all the parents need to hear to know that everything they did for the child was utterly worthy.

Hurdles Encountered

For the hurdles encountered, the conversational partners emphasized the hurdles they encountered, which include limited knowledge due to educational background, different household activities, and the emotional state of giving up. The reality in the educational process is that some parents can help their children to comply with the Modular Learning requirements. However, this depends on the assistance of parents for those who cannot comply fully with the modules. Parents with enough educational background can exert their knowledge to answer the modules, but there are cases when compliance with the modular contents is complex if parents have a limited educational background. The responses revealed that limited knowledge due to educational background is also a challenge and a problem in assisting their children in their modular learning.

This implies that some parents had difficulty dealing

with the content of the learning modules and that the parent's involvement in the educational process is very significant even if they have limited knowledge but have tried to cope with the requirements of modular learning for their children to meet their educational goals.

This finding supports Dangle and Sumaoang (2020) on the implementation of modular distance learning in the Philippines, which revealed that parents' lack of knowledge to guide their children academically is one of the main challenges the implementation brings to such a learning modality. (Gevero, 2021) similarly, parents complained that the time allotted to complete the module's activities was insufficient because there were so many activities in such a short period. Some parents stated that due to a lack of proper education, parents could not provide learners with knowledge that they could utilize to assist their children in completing their learning modules.

The different household activities sometimes affect the parents' assistance as a buddy to their children's modules. Home responsibilities are sometimes prioritized, but parents' involvement in their children's education motivates them to consider assistance to their children as part of their duties and responsibilities. Household activities require priorities by parents to cope with the responsibilities of maintaining typical family situations. Balancing time for the household and helping the children do their modules require proper planning. This finding implies that despite the parent's significant role in complying with household activities, the education of their children is given more priority for future development. In addition, parents balance their time doing household chores and answering modules with their children. This result is in line with the statement of Eccles and Harold (2010) that parental involvement outside the classroom is done at home, termed home-based parental involvement, where parents are directly involving themselves related to school work, including assisting with homework and responding to children's academic choices and academic issues. So to cope with the modular learning of children, parents balance their time to help their children and do their household responsibilities. There are cases when the result of the conversational discussion indicates that the conversational partner articulated all the answers and developed an emotional state of giving up. Sometimes, parents lose hope in helping their children due to being busy with household chores, jobs, and other responsibilities, tiredness, and difficulty; they develop perseverance, and some never give up on helping their children.

The implication of this finding shows that there are cases of emotional crisis that sometimes develop the feeling of giving up but are overcome by spending time to relax, normalizing the emotional crisis. In addition, parents are sometimes experiencing difficulty due to some challenging experiences, which affect emotions that sometimes develop discouragement and intend to give up. This study is supported by Shaira Kaye O. Degamo; Jennylyn E. Sano stated that the Parents of children with special needs encountered similar experiences in handling their children's educational needs during this new normal of education. However, parents still try their best to teach their children the best way they could. Parents who struggle to teach their children became more active and vigilant in attending the needs of their children. The statement upholds this situation that parents' feelings towards remote learning are mixed. Some parents feel more connected to their child's schoolwork, while others see this as an additional burden (Gevero, 2021).

Conquering Difficulties

Sometimes, parents lose hope in helping their children due to being busy with household chores, jobs, and other responsibilities, tiredness, and difficulty; they develop perseverance, and some never give up on helping their children. In times of conflict of priorities of parents between the household chores or job and helping the children in their modules, balancing time for housework and helping children in their modules need proper planning does setting priorities through appropriate planning important based on the responses of partners' significant statements. This means that planning the time to do what is necessary will enhance the excellence of learners' performance. Time management entails setting aside time for tasks that will advance objectives. It implies that having time management will create the best time in helping their children in answering their modules at home. Furthermore, doing lots of works without time management neglects tutoring children with their module. Moreover, parental involvement, whether in school or at home, strengthens the bond between parents and their children, improves their children's proper behavior, and enhances academic performance. This further implies that proper planning will minimize conflict of priorities.

This is related to the statement of Sheldon, Mussof, and Philip (2021) that "Maintaining the parent-child relationship is so important" and indicated that as parents, there is a need to consider the child's individual needs, relationship with the child, and how

academic work plays into it. In cases of challenges on Modular Compliance, which developed discouragement, praying to God's guidance is one option for parents to assist the learners. The difficulties encountered can be conquered by trusting God's guidance. Praying for God's guidance is the strategy to be guided to conquer difficulties usually experienced by children and parents in their studies. This implies that the challenges encountered every day can be provided with guidance through God's constant prayer. Further, the constant prayer of parents for God's guidance will help improve children's education. Research has shown that parental involvement in their children's education improves their educational achievements from early childhood, causes them to stay longer in school, and encourages overall positive development, as emphasized by Lehmann, E., (2020) but strengthened by the trust of parents to God's guidance because according to Hebrew 13:6, God will help those who ask help and should not feel afraid. So, the trust of parents in the help of God exhibited by constant prayer strengthens parental involvement.

Unity and cooperation among family members has a great impact on the learning of the students. A harmonious relationship with family members can strengthen compliance with the Modular Learning requirements. Family assistance, especially the parents, can contribute to the output quality. Based on the responses of the conversational partners the modular learning program strengthens the family relationship. Each family member shows concern, unity, and cooperation in helping children with their learning modules. Parents sometimes ask for help from their neighbors and children's classmates. This implies that every parent has different experiences and situations and in times of deficiencies of the needed competence, asking neighbor's help is the adopted option. This situation also implies that parents significantly contribute to completing the Modular requirements.

This finding supports the statement of Newman (2019) that learning at home provides information and ideas to families about how to help students at home with homework and other curriculum-related activities, decisions, and planning and the statement of (Wang et al., 2020) that when parents and their children spend more time together, it is likely said to be a good bond where they can have more time working together in a child's learning activities. In addition, it states that the more parents are open and have time with their children may result in allowing their children to understand that they are present in times when they need hope, and comfort, easing their pain and worry.

As suggested by (Zahed, Rezaee, Yazdani, Bagheri, and Nabeiei, 2016), it is a highly significant component of parenting associated with the training and growth of talents, skills, the learning about social rules and norms, as well as choices of interests in the forms of hobbies that can transform in careers when both are having close relationships and mutual understanding between parents and children. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that high levels of parents' involvement in the learning and disciplining of children could have a reverse effect on accomplishment according to (Hosokawa & Katsura, 2018). Furthermore, Hamaidi et al. (2021) expounded that family members are the first and most important influences on the learning of children of all ages. While parents are usually the most substantial models and have the most significant impact, grandparents, aunts, uncles, and family friends can act as role models, aides, and encouragers. These influences often shape input from peers, neighbors, teachers, and others.

Conclusion

Parents or guardians are partners of teachers in education. They serve as home facilitators and para-teachers who facilitate and guide the students in answering the modular lessons they sent during the modular learnings.

As a teacher the parents' primary role in modular learning is to establish well the connection and guidance to their children towards answering their modules.

Parents encountered the limited knowledge due to the educational background, the complexity of different household activities and the feeling of complication of responsibilities that some developed emotional state of giving up.

It implies that not only the children learn during this modular class but also the parents. It develops their knowledge and skills and gives their ideas to continue studying. Due the new partnership between institutions and parents, a mutually beneficial hub of learning and innovation is developed, assuring continued studies by guiding children with their modules; it allows to parents learn more. While parents help their kids with their modules, they also learn.

Self-related perceptions of the self should be enhanced through the school's environment and learning activities. Despite that, it can be assumed that higher

self-concept will not predict academic performance; either way, students' academic performance does not reflect on their self-concept. Likewise, it should be noted that the respondents were still in the process of searching for their unique identities. Further, students need extensive educational learning experience from the school and their environment to harness their skills and develop their self-efficacy.

References

- Ali, W. (2020). Online and remote learning in higher education institutes: a necessity in light of COVID-19 pandemic.
- Ali, I. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic: making sense of rumor and fear. *Med Anthropol*. 1–4. doi: 10.1080/01459740.2020 Google Scholar
- Alicamen, D. et al. (2020). Parents as Study Buddy in the New Normal of Teaching: A Grounded Theory https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349462922_Parents_as_Study_Buddy_in_the_New_Normal_of_Teaching_A_Grounded_Theory
- Ambayon, C. M. (2020). Modular-Based Approach and Students' Achievement in Literature. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 8(3), 32–36. <https://doi.org/10.7575/AIAC.IJELS.V.8N.3P.32>
- Arifin, (2018). Ethical Considerations in Qualitative Study
- Borup, J., Graham, C. R., & Davies, R. S. (2013). The nature of parental interactions in an online charter school. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 27(1), 40-55. doi: 10.1080/08923647.2013.754271
- Borup, J., Stevens, M. A., & Waters, L. H. (2015). Parent and student perceptions of parent engagement at a cyber charter high school. *Online Learning*, 19(5), 69–91. Retrieved March 25, 2021, from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1085792>
- Bhadari, (2020). What is Qualitative Research?
- Branquinho, C, Kelly, C, Arevalo, LC, Santos, A, Gaspar de Matos, M. (2020). "Hey, we also have something to say": a qualitative study of Portuguese adolescents' and young people's experiences under COVID-19. *J Community Psychol*. 2020; 48: 2740– 2752. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcop.22453>
- Cahapay, M. (2021), Involvement of Parents in Remote Learning of Children amid COVID-19 Crisis in the Ph *International Journal of Sociology of Education 2021ilippines: A Transcendental Phenomenology* https://papers.ssm.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3825316
- Canonizado, I. C. (2021). Challenges that Teachers Are Facing Under the New Normal System in Education. *HubPages*. Retrieved from <https://discover.hubpages.com/education/Challenges-that-Teachers-Are-Facing-Under-the-New-Normal-System-in-Education> <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0236337>
- Castro, M., Exposito-Casas, E., Lopez-Martin, E., Lizasoain, L.,

Navarro-Asencio, E., &

for Successful Education e p s Journal | Vol.7 | No. 3

Luis Gaviria, J. (2015). Parental involvement on student academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 14, 33–46. [10.1016/j.edurev.2015.01.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.01.002)

Ceka, A., & Murati, R. (2016). The Role of Parents in the Education of Children. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(5), 61-64.

Colaizzi, P. (1978). Psychological research as a phenomenologist view it. In: Valle, R. S. & King, M. (1978). *Existential phenomenological alternatives for psychology*, open university press: New York.

Cooper, H., Lindsay, J. J., & Nye, B. (2000). Homework in the home: How student, family, and parenting- style differences relate to the homework process. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(4), 464–487.

Curtis, H. (2013). A mixed methods study investigating parental involvement and student success in high school online education (Doctoral dissertation). Northwest Nazarene University,

Curtis, H., & Werth, L. (2015). Fostering student success and engagement in a K-12 online school. *Journal of Online Learning Research*, 1(2), 163–190. Retrieved March 25, 2021, from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1148836>

Chandra, Y. (2021). "Online education during COVID-19: perception of academic stress and emotional intelligence coping strategies among college students", *Asian Education and Development Studies*, Vol. 10 No. 2, pp. 229-238. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/AEDS-05-2020-0097>

Crutsinger, C. (2021). Time Management, Thinking Smarter: Skills for Academic Success at <https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-is-time-management-definition-examples-studies.html>

Dangle, Y. & Sumaoang, J. (2020). The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in the Philippine Secondary Public School. The 3rd International Conference on Academic Research in Science, Technology and Engineering, Ireland.

Degamo, S. & Sano, J. (2021) Challenges of Parents with Children with Special Needs in the New Normal <https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT21AUG563.pdf>

Department of Education Order No. 12 s. 2020. (n.d.). Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in light of the Covid-19 Public Health Emergency Department of Education (DepEd, 2020). Memoranda related to COVID-19. Retrieved from: <https://www.deped.gov.ph/covid-19/covid19-memoranda/>

Department of Education Division Memorandum No. 265, s. 2020. (n.d.). Module key Dates

Department of Education Order No. 18 s. 2020. (n.d.). Policy-Guidelines-for-the-Provision of-Learning-Resources-in-the-Implementation-of-the-Basic-Education LearningContinuity-Plan.pdf

Department of Education Order No. 001 s. 2021. (n.d.). self learning modules evaluation guidelines.pdf

Dong, C., Cao, S., Li, H (2020), Children's Online Learning during COVID-19 pandemic: Chinese parents' beliefs and attitudes. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105440>

Duriscic, M., et al., (2017). Parental Involvement as a Important Factor

Ellis, E., Dumas, M., and Forbes, M. (2020). Physically isolated but socially connected: psychological adjustment and stress among adolescents during the initial COVID-19 crisis. *Canadian Journal of Behavioural Science / Revue canadienne des sciences du comportement*, 52(3), 177-187. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/cbs0000215>

Elmer, T., Mepham, K., and Stadtfeld, C. (2020). Students under lockdown: Comparisons of students' social networks and mental health before and during the COVID-19 crisis in Switzerland. *PLOS ONE* 15(7): e0236337. Retrieved from:

Garbe, A., Ogurlu U., Logan, N. & Cook, P. (2020). Covid-19 and remote learning: experiences of parents with children during the pandemic. *American Journal of Qualitative Research*. 4(3), 45-65. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ajqr/8471>

Gevero, M. (2021). Engagement of parents on modular teaching approach: a literature review. *Global Scientific Journals*. 9(10). ISSN 22320-9186 <https://www.globalscientificjournal.com/>

Hamaidi, D., Arouri, Y., Noufal, R. & Aldrou, I. (2021). Parents' perceptions of their children's experiences with distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*. (22)2. <https://www.irrodl.org/index.php/irrodl/article/view/5154/5495>

Hasan, S. (2020). Schools close, children free -parents face a new conundrum. Retrieved from <https://www.dawn.com/news/1540682/schools-close-children-free-parents-face-new-conundrum>

Hasler-Waters, L., Borup, J., & Menchaca, D. M. P. (2018). Parental involvement in K-12 online and blended learning. In K. Kennedy & R. Ferdig (Eds.), *Handbook of research on K-12 online and blended learning* (2nd ed.; pp. 403-422). ETC Press. Retrieved from [http://press.etc.cmu.edu/index.php/product/handbook-of-research-on-k-12-and-blending-learning-second-edition/Hoover-Dempsey, K. V., & Sandler, H. \(1995\). Parental involvement in children's FINAL REPORT, OERI/IES GRANT #R305T010673 69](http://press.etc.cmu.edu/index.php/product/handbook-of-research-on-k-12-and-blending-learning-second-edition/Hoover-Dempsey, K. V., & Sandler, H. (1995). Parental involvement in children's FINAL REPORT, OERI/IES GRANT #R305T010673 69)

Hoover-Dempsey, K. V., & Sandler, H. (1997). Why do parents become involved in their children's education? *Review of Educational Research*, 67(1), 3-42.

Hosokawa & Katsura, (2018). Role of Parenting Style in Children's Behavioral Problems through the Transition from Preschool to Elementary School According to Gender in Japan

Ibyatova, L., Oparina, K., & Rakova, E. (2018). MODULAR APPROACH TO TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH GRAMMAR IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES. SOCIETY. INTEGRATION. EDUCATION. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference, 1, 139 – 148. <https://doi.org/10.17770/SIE2018VOL1.3229>

Jaiswal, K. S. (2017). Role of Parental Involvement and Some Strategies that Promote Parental Involvement.

Keaton, W., & Gilbert, A. (2020). Successful online learning: What does learner interaction with peers, instructors and parents look like? *Journal of Online Learning Research*, 6(2), 129– 154. Retrieved March 25, 2021, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1273659.pdf>

Kim, S. W. (2020). Meta-analysis of parental involvement and achievement in east Asian countries. *Education and Urban Society*, 52(2), 312–337. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013124519842654>

- LaRocque, M., Kleiman, I., & Darling, S.M. (2011). Parental Involvement: The Missing Link in School Achievement. Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth, 55(3), 115-122. doi:10.1080/10459880903472876
- Lee, S.J., Ward, K.P., & Chang, O.D. (2020). Research brief: Parents' perceptions of the shift to homebased education during the Covid-19 pandemic. Ann Arbor, MI: University of Michigan Parenting in Context Research Lab. Retrieved from https://www.parentingincontext.org/uploads/8/1/3/1/81318622/research_brief_parents%20%80%99_%20%20perceptions_of_the_shift_to_home-based_education_during_the_covid-19_pandemic_final.pdf
- Lee et al., (2022). Effects of a workplace intervention on daily stressor reactivity
- Lehmann, E., (2020). How Latino Parents Perceive the Invitation of Parental Involvement
- Lincoln, Y., & Guba, E. G. (1985). Naturalistic inquiry. Newbury park, CA: Sage. [https://www.parentingincontext.org/uploads/8/1/3/1/81318622/research_brief_parents%20%80%99_%20%20https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=2oA9aWlNeoc&oi=fnd&pg=PA7&dq=Lincoln,+Y.,+%26+Guba,+E.+G.+\(1985\).+Naturalistic+inquiry.+Newbury+Park,+CA:+Sage.&ots=0uouXaVfyr&sig=NcnRlXCYpA8Wk9e2IsaGJibMIM&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false](https://www.parentingincontext.org/uploads/8/1/3/1/81318622/research_brief_parents%20%80%99_%20%20https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=2oA9aWlNeoc&oi=fnd&pg=PA7&dq=Lincoln,+Y.,+%26+Guba,+E.+G.+(1985).+Naturalistic+inquiry.+Newbury+Park,+CA:+Sage.&ots=0uouXaVfyr&sig=NcnRlXCYpA8Wk9e2IsaGJibMIM&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false)
- Luaña, J. P. (2021). Why do Parents Answer their Children's Modules? A Closer Look on Parental Practices and Challenges in Modular Distance Learning. International Journal of Global Community, 4(1 -March), 1 -16.
- Manila Times. (2020, July 30). Crucial role parents play in children's continuous learning. Author. Retrieved from <https://www.manilatimes.net/2020/07/30/campus-press/crucial-role-parentsplay-in-childrens-continuous-learning/747924/a>
- Manlangit, P., Paglumotan, A. M., & Saperas, S. C. (2020, October 5). Nanay, handa na ba kayong maging tagapagdaloy? Supercharging Filipino parents is key for successful modular distance learning. *Flip Science*. <https://www.flipscience.ph/news/featuresnews/tagapagdaloy-modular-distance-learning/>
- Mercader, H. L., & Abadiano, M. N., (2020). Kaleidoscopic Features of Home Tutorial in Modular Distance Learning: A Confession of Functional Illiterate Parents. <http://www.psychologyandeducation.net/pae/index.php/pae/article/view/4008>
- Milles, K. (2020). Effectiveness of modular approach in teaching at the university level. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(17), 104. http://www.academia.edu/download/37300040/Sadia_Dr_shazia.pdf
- Morin, C.M., Carrier, J., Bastien, C. et al. (2020). Sleep and circadian rhythm in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Canadian Journal of Public Health 111, 654-657. Available: http://www.academia.edu/download/37300040/Sadia_Dr_shazia.pdf
- McCarthy K.M.Ed (2022). Thank you Parents: Expressions of Gratitude for Lifetime Love. At <https://family.love toknow.com?family-quotes-every-situation/thank-you-parents-expressions-gratitude-lifetime-love>.
- Newman, (2019). Epstein's Model of Parental Involvement: Parent Perceptions in Urban Schools
- Paco, D., Yazon, A., Manaig, K, Sapin, S. & Bandoy, M. (2021). Paint a portrait: lived experience of parents in implementing modular distance learning. *International Journal on Research in STEM Education*, 3(2), 901-911. ISSN 2721-2904
- Parent Zone (2020). Home Learning Environment
- Philippine Information agency, (2020). The Lens of Education in The Philippines: The New Normal
- Ratih, K., Syah, M. F. J., Nurhidayat, N., Jarin, S., & Buckworth, J. (2021). Learning patterns during the disruptive situation in informal education: Parents' efforts and challenges in the adjustment of progressive learning. *Indonesian Journal on Learning and Advanced Education*, 3(3), 180-193. <https://doi.org/10.23917/ijolae.v3i3.15151>
- Saeed, A. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 on education in Pakistan. Retrieved from <https://www.matrixmag.com/the-impact-of-covid-19-on-education-in-pakistan/>
- Seale, C. (2020). Distance Learning During the Coronavirus Pandemic: Equity And Access Questions For School Leaders
- Sheldon, H., Mussof, J., and Philip, L.(2021). How to set Priorities this School Year, At <https://childmind.org/article-how-to-set-priorities-this-school-year>.
- SyedaRakhshandaKaukab (2016). The Impact of Parent/Family Involvement on Student's Learning Outcomes
- Tererani al., (2015). Choosing a Qualitative Research Approach <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-D-15-00414.1>
- Tibon, J. (2020). The New Normal in Basic Education. ACCRALAW. <https://www.lexology.com/library>
- UNESCO (2020). COVID-19 Educational Disruption and Response. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>
- UNESCO (2020). COVID-19 Educational disruption and response. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-emergencies/coronavirus-school-closures>
- UNESCO (2020, February 19). How is China ensuring learning when classes are disrupted by coronavirus? Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/news/how-china-ensuring-learning-when-classes-are-disrupted-coronavirus>.
- Unicef (2020). Providing youth a second chance to complete their education amid COVID-19 A case study on Education in emergencies in the Philippines. Available: <https://www.unicef.org/philippines/stories/providing-youth-second-chance-complete-their-education-amid-covid-19> University of Minnesota (2018). Version of Parental Involvement Model
- Walker, K. (2021). Strategies to Support Teacher Well-Being and Retention Amid the COVID-19 Pandemic. Available: <https://www.waldenu.edu/online-masters-programs/master-of-arts-in-teaching/resource/strategies-to-support-teacher-well-being-and-retention-amid-the-covid-19-pandemic>
- Wang, G., Zhang, Y., Zhao, J., Zhang, J., & Jiang, F. (2020). Mitigate the effects of home confinement on children during the COVID-19 outbreak. *The Lancet*, 395(10228), 945-947
- World Health Organization. (2020). Mental health and psychosocial considerations during the COVID-19 outbreak. Retrieved from: <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/mental-health>

-considerations.pdf

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Yousafzai, A., (2020) Low-cost private Schools May not be Able to Survive the COVID-19 crisis
Available:<https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/637486-low-cost-private-schools-maynot-be-able-to-survive-covid-19-crisis>

Joel C. Gutierrez, MAEd
Malamote National High School
Department of Education - Philippines

Zahed, Rezaee, Yazdani, Bagheri, and Nabeiei (2016). The influence of parenting style on academic achievement and career path